

THEORETICAL ASPECTS FOR ECONOMIC SECURITY AND INFLUENCING FACTORS

Nematjanov Bekhzod Bakhtiyor ugli

Researcher At Tashkent State University of Economics Tashkent, Uzbekistan
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Abstract: This thesis delves into the multifaceted concept of economic security, examining its definitions, dimensions, and implications for individuals and nations. By analyzing various economic policies, social safety nets, and global economic trends, the research aims to highlight the ultimate factors that contribute to a secure economic environment. The findings suggest that comprehensive strategies, including income stability, access to resources, and resilience against economic shocks, are essential for fostering long-term economic security.

Key words: economic security, national security, state, sustainable development, economic growth.

The issue of economic security is highly significant for the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is increasingly integrating into the global economy. Furthermore, the country's location in a politically unstable region enhances the relevance of this direction for our nation.

Economic security forms the fundamental basis of a state's overall economic efficiency. Broadly defined, "an economically effective state is one that defends its national interests and ensures national economic security at a given time and under specific circumstances amidst unrestricted international competition" [2].

There has been extensive research in economic literature on the improvement of economic security. However, there is insufficient coverage of the role of the real sector in enhancing economic security through the influence of various factors. This indicates not only the high relevance of the research topic but also the practical significance of the real sector's role in ensuring economic security in Uzbekistan under current conditions.

The concepts, significance, types, and mechanisms of national and international economic security have been studied by foreign economists such as H. Brundtland, D. Gabor, P. Krugman, K. Sen, E. Laszlo, and J. Forrester. Among Russian scholars, significant contributions have been made by L.I. Abalkin, S.Y. Glazyev, A.E. Gorodetsky, V.S. Zagashvili, I.D. Ivanov, A.I. Illarionov, A. Gamza, S.I. Zelgin, A.V. Krysin, A.G. Shavaev, and V.I. Yarochenko.

Uzbek researchers, including N. Djumaev, K. Abulkosimov, D. Davronov, A. Vakhidov, A. Abduvohidov, R. Makhmudov, I. Mavlyanov, and U. Hasanov, have also conducted studies and researches on economic security issues.

G.G. Odunova notes, “security is of significant interest for regional economies. The national security system is a multi-level structure where the region acts as both a subject and a space for implementing security policies. Currently, globalization is a major factor affecting regions, creating threats to their socio-economic development. In response to these threats, regions strive to expand their powers to ensure long-term security” [3].

Research by Abduvohidov A. and others highlights that economic security “represents a state of the economy where stable economic growth is ensured, social needs are optimally met, rational management is implemented, and economic interests are protected at both national and international levels” [4].

E. Ilichin has conducted research on the fundamentals of forming an economic security system, the role and place of ensuring economic security in banking activities within the economic security system, and has evaluated the current state of economic security in the banking sector by identifying threats and risks [5].

Given these considerations, the concept of "economic security" can be understood as a set of conditions and factors that ensure the stability of the national economy and its ability to continuously renew and improve itself.

Ensuring economic security is of particular importance in countries undergoing transitions to a market economy. These changes inevitably affect adaptation mechanisms, interests, and the economic activities of business entities. This demonstrates that economic security is interrelated with its goals, strategy, and implementation priorities.

Economic security refers to the stability and resilience of an individual's or a nation's economic well-being. It encompasses various factors that ensure access to basic needs, financial resources, and opportunities for growth. Here are some key factors influencing economic security:

1. Employment Opportunities

Job Availability: A strong job market with diverse opportunities enhances economic security.

Job Quality: Stability, benefits, and wages associated with jobs contribute significantly to economic well-being.

2. Income Stability

Wages: Competitive wages and equitable pay are critical for sustaining economic security.

Income Diversification: Multiple income streams can provide a safety net during economic downturns.

3. Social Safety Nets

Welfare Programs: Government assistance programs, such as unemployment benefits, food assistance, and healthcare, help mitigate financial crises.

Retirement Benefits: Access to pensions and retirement savings plans supports long-term economic stability.

4. Education and Skill Development

Access to Education: Quality education and vocational training increase employability and adaptability in changing job markets.

Lifelong Learning: Continuous skill development helps individuals stay relevant in evolving industries.

5. Healthcare Access

Affordable Healthcare: Access to healthcare services reduces financial burdens related to medical expenses and promotes a healthier workforce.

6. Financial Literacy

Understanding Financial Management: Knowledge of budgeting, saving, and investing can empower individuals to make informed financial decisions.

7. Economic Policies

Fiscal and Monetary Policies: Government policies that promote economic growth, control inflation, and stabilize markets directly influence economic security.

Regulation: Effective regulation can protect consumers and promote fair competition, enhancing economic stability.

8. Social Cohesion

Community Support Systems: Strong community networks can provide support during economic hardships.

Social Inclusion: Reducing inequality and promoting equal opportunities can enhance overall economic security.

9. Political Stability

Governance: Stable political environments tend to attract investment and foster economic growth, contributing to overall security.

10. Global Economic Factors

Trade Policies: International trade agreements can create new economic opportunities or pose risks.

Global Economic Trends: Economic fluctuations, such as recessions or booms in other countries, can impact domestic economic security.

Economic security is multifaceted, relying on a combination of individual, social, and governmental factors. Strengthening these elements can help build a more resilient economic environment for individuals and communities alike

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